

Investigation of the Antileishmanial Activity of *Medicago sativa* Extract: An *in vitro* Study

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Summary

Leishmaniasis is a group of parasitic diseases caused by various species of *Leishmania*. Cutaneous manifestations of the disease can cause protracted wounds, difficult to heal, thus it is important to discover novel compounds that can augment in wound healing. The aim of this study is to investigate antileishmanial activity of *Medicago sativa* extract. Parasites were treated with different concentrations of plant extract (5, 100, 250, 500 and 1000 µg/ml) for 24, 48, and 72 hours. The characterization was done by reversed phase-high performance liquid chro-

matography (RP-HPLC). The IC₅₀ values were 566.62, 445.74, and 375.74 after 24, 48, and 72 hours incubation, respectively. The results showed that the survival of this parasite can be limited by increasing the incubation time and/or the extraction dosage. The analysis of extract showed that this extract includes phenolic and flavonoid compounds. The total phenolic value was more than total flavonoids compounds. The anti-*Leishmania* activity of *M. sativa* extract may be due to the high concentration of phenolic compounds, especially caffeic acid. From our results, it can be suggested that the *M. sativa* extract is a potential herbal drug against leishmaniasis.

Key words

IC₅₀, *Leishmania*, *Medicago sativa*, phenols, flavonoids, wound healing

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Introduction

Leishmaniasis is a group of parasitic diseases caused by various species of *Leishmania*. *Leishmania* is a member of Trypanosomatidae family and it can be seen in two forms during its life cycle: promastigotes seen in invertebrates and culture medium¹⁻³ and intracellular amastigotes seen in reticuloendothelial cells and skin of vertebrates.⁴ There are four forms of leishmaniasis: cutaneous, mucocutaneous, visceral, and post-kala-azar dermal leishmaniasis (PKDL). Untreated visceral leishmaniasis can be fatal.⁵ World Health Organization (WHO) includes this disease among the eight important parasitic disease in the world. It is estimated that 350 million people worldwide are at risk of developing the disease and almost 12 million people are affected, mostly in the tropical and subtropical regions. Annually, 1 to 5.1 million new patients will be added in 88 countries, with the vast majority of patients, reaching 90%, exhibiting cutaneous leishmaniasis. The majority of skin ulcers caused by *L. major*/*L. tropica* recover in a few weeks to several months without treatment. The parasites can cause severe wounds that improve after several⁶⁻⁸ months of treatment. Multiple treatments have been sugge-

sted for the disease, but there is no effective treatment for it. Pentavalent antimony derivatives (sodium stibogluconate, meglumine antimoniate), are actually the first line of treatment.^{9,10} The goal of the treatment is rapid scar-free healing of wounds, and prevention of secondary infection. Typically combinations of pentavalent antimony such as meglumine antimoniate are used for the treatment of cutaneous leishmaniasis. The use of these agent though is complicated by side effects such as liver disorders, cardiovascular and biochemical changes because of inherent dose-dependent toxicity and frequency of injection.¹² Furthermore, resistance to antimony has increased in recent years leading to introduction of some new antileishmanial compounds such as miltefosine. However, all of these drugs have different side effects.¹³ In between, extensive studies have been conducted on plant extracts and compounds.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Natural or plant-derived compounds are widely used for inhibition of pathogenic microorganisms.¹⁷⁻²⁰ Since herbal medicines are available and cheap and have no adverse effects, their use, according to local flora, has been emphasized.² *M. sativa* is used for the treatment of diverse clinical conditions, including arthritis and edema. This plant contains a lot of vitamins A and

C and thus, it may prevent bleeding and help in wound healing, vitamin C deficiency, and anemia (due to its high iron content).¹⁴ *M. sativa* exists in cold mountain areas. It has also been proposed that this herb can cure diabetes, but there are no studies about its effects on wound healing of Leishmania and its impact on promastigote.²¹ The discovery of new drugs increasing wound healing is very important for the treatment of cutaneous Leishmaniasis. The present study aimed at investigating the effect of *Medicago sativa* fresh juice, used in wound healing, on the *in vitro* survival of promastigotes.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of the alcoholic extract

In this study, the shoots of *M. sativa* were collected from Yazd province. After drying at 37°C, extraction was done by soaking method at temperatures of 15-20°C with 75% ethanol. For this purpose, 1000 ml of ethanol (75%) is poured on 100 grams of plant powder so that powder is completely covered. The mixture is placed on a shaker for better extraction of active ingredients. After 48 hours, solution was passed from Whatman® filter paper. The filtrated solution was concentrated by a vacuum distillation unit (rotator) and thus, it was reduced to one-third of the original volume.

Culture of *L. major* parasites

Strain of *L. major* parasites (MRHO / IR / 75 / ER) were obtained from Shahid Sadoughi University of Medical Sciences, Yazd, Iran. The Novy-MacNeal-Nicolle medium (NNN) (containing sodium chloride, glucose, brain heart infusion (BHI), heparinized blood of rabbits and agar) was used for culture of parasites. The flask was examined (under 25°C and every 48 h) for the absence of contamination by fungi and bacteria, as well as the growth of promastigotes. Flask was repeatedly examined until promastigote concentration reached one million parasites per ml.

Treatment of Leishmania with extract

One million/ml of parasites was counted using neobar lam and one ml of this concentration was poured in each tube. Seven groups were evaluated:

Group I: Exposure to 5 µg/ml of extract; Group II: Exposure to 100µg/ml of extract; Group III: Exposure to 250 µg/ml of extract; Group D: Exposure to 500 µg/ml of extract; Group E: Exposure to 1000 µg/ml of extract; Group F (control group): there is no treatment; and Group G (sterile saline control group): Exposure to sterile saline serum

Evaluation of anti-Leishmanial activity

All groups were examined in terms of the number and activity after 24, 48, and 72 hours. Counting was done by neobar lam. Amphotericin B was used as positive control. Growth inhibitory (GI) was calculated by the equation: % GI= $(1 - \text{GR}_{\text{extract}} / \text{GR}_{\text{control}}) \times 100$, where GR=growth rate. Then, half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC50) was calculated by SigmaPlot™13 software (Systat Software Inc., USA) in different times and concentrations.

Determination of total compounds of extract

Total phenolic and flavonoid compounds of the extract was determined by colorimetric method. Briefly, for determination of phenolic and flavonoid, the extract was measured at absorbance 765 and 510 nm, respectively. For further analysis, reversed phase-high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) was used. In this quantitative mode, allic acid, syringic acid, pyrogallol, salicylic acid, and caffeic acid were used for standard curve for phenolic compounds and quercetin, rutin, myricetin, kaempferol, naringin and apigenin were used for standard curve for flavonoid compounds. Elution was performed using solution A [0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) in water] combined with a 5 to 65% gradient of solution B [0.098% TFA in acetonitrile] over a period of 65 min, at a flow rate of 2 ml/min. According to the absorbance at 280 nm for phenolic compound and 350nm for flavonoid compounds, the fractions were characterized.

Results

Extract analysis

Seven compounds were characterized from *M. sativa* extract using RP-HPLC technique. Phenolic compounds included gallic acid, pyrogallol, salicylic acid, caffeic acid, while flavonoid compounds included naringenin, quercetin, and myricetin (Figure 1 and 2). The concentration of phenolic compounds [46.26 mg/g dry mass (DM)] was more than flavonoid compounds [18.65 mg Eq./g DM]. The highest concentration belonged to caffeic acid [726.32 µg/g DM] (Table 1).

Antileishmanial activity

The result of antileishmanial activity of *M. sativa* extract was shown in Figure 3. The ethanol extracts had potent activity against Leishmania. The antileishmanial activity increased along with increase of extract concentration. This relationship was linear in concentrations greater than 400 µg/ml. The IC50 was 566.62, 445.74, and 375.74 after 24, 48, and 72 hours, respectively.

Figure 1 The RP-HPLC of phenolic compounds in *M. sativa* extract.

Figure 2 The RP-HPLC of flavonoid compounds in *M. sativa* extract.

Table 1 Total phenolic and flavonoid compounds as well as phenolic and flavonoid contents in <i>M. sativa</i> extract			
Total compounds	value	Phenolic and flavonoid contents	Value ($\mu\text{g g/g DM}$)
Total phenolic	46.26 mg /g DM	Gallic acid	352.12
		Pyrogallol	425.12
		Caffeic acid	726.32
		salicylic acid	128.3
Total flavonoid	18.65 mg eq./g DM	naringenin	498.3
		quercetin	572.6
		Myricetin	365.4

Figure 3

Antileishmanial activity of *M. sativa* extract after 24, 48, and 72 hours incubation.

Discussion

The consequences of the long duration of and the scars caused by the cutaneous leishmaniasis, the role of human and animal reservoirs, the obstacles in the disease vector control (such as sandfly species diversity) render research on the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of this disease very important and necessary, especially in endemic countries such as Iran.¹¹ In the

classical treatment for leishmaniasis administration of toxic and poorly tolerated drugs such as pentavalent antimony derivatives, pentamidine, and amphotericin B is used. Moreover, there are no effective vaccines to prevent leishmaniasis.^{26,27} Herbal compounds are a potential source of new compounds with suitable biological activities. These compounds have different activities such as antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antioxidant, anticancer, and antiprotozoal activity.

These activities correspond to diverse chemical groups in plant extracts.¹⁷⁻²⁰ Since fresh juice of *M. sativa* is traditionally used in wound healing, we investigated the effect of *M. sativa* extract on Leishmania parasites.¹⁴ The characterization of extract showed that this extract includes many phenolic and flavonoid compounds. The content of phenolic compounds was more than flavonoid compounds. Between phenolic compounds, the highest value belonged to caffeic acid. Other studies showed almost similar compounds for *M. sativa* leaves extract, but their quantity was different. In all studies, the content of phenolic compounds was more than flavonoid compounds. Functional properties including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and xanthine oxidase (XO) inhibitory activities were previously reported for *M. sativa* extract.²⁸⁻³¹ We found that the ethanol extracts had also potent activity against Leishmania. The antileishmanial activity increased along with increase of extract concentration. This relationship was linear in concentrations greater than 400 µg/ml. An increase in incubation time from 24 to 72 hours led to a higher activity (IC₅₀=566.62, 445.74, and 375.74 after 24, 48, and 72 hours, respectively.) Tasdemir et al investigated the *in vivo* antileishmanial activity of six flavonoids: luteolin, luteolin-7-O-glucoside, 3-hydroxyflavone, fisetin, quercetin, and myricetin. The result of this study showed that only quercetin had activity by inhibiting the infection by 15.3% and all other flavonoids were inactive.³² In our extract, there was quercetin as flavonoid compound, thus its antileishmanial activity may be due to this agent. Vila-Nova et al showed that quercetin and rutin have leishmanicidal activity in both the promastigote and amastigote stages. Their activity was similar to that of pentamidine and amphotericin B, established agents used to treat leishmaniasis.³³ Researchers also studied the potential antileishmanial activity of phenolic compounds, such as caffeic acid, ferulic acid, syringic acid.³⁴⁻³⁶ The activity of phenolic compounds, especially

caffeic acid, on Leishmania parasites have been proven.^{33,37,38} *M. sativa* extract had high concentrations of phenolic compounds, especially caffeic acid. Thus, *M. sativa* extract's potent antileishmanial activity may be due to phenolic and flavonoid compounds (quercetin and caffeic acid). A proposed mechanism for antileishmanial activity might include the flavonoids binding to the nucleotide binding domains (NBD) of Leishmania ATP binding cassette (ABC) transporters.³⁹

Different researches showed the potent effect of *M. sativa* extract on wound healing. These studies indicated that *M. sativa* extract increased the wound healing because of vitamin A and C content.⁴⁰ In endemic countries with high prevalence of leishmaniasis, healing of ulcerative lesions is delayed by bacterial and/or fungal infections. So, it can cause severe wounds that improve after several months of treatment.^{41,42} According to previous studies and results derived from this study, *M. sativa* extract has potent antileishmanial and wound healing activity. Thus, this extract can inhibit parasite growth and heal the related wound.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of his study showed that the *M. sativa* extract has highly leishmanicidal activity. Thus, the *M. sativa* extract is a potential herbal drug against leishmaniasis as well as wound healing caused by Leishmania. Further experiments need to be done in order to investigate *M. sativa* extract's anti-Leishmanial activity in animal models.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Περίληψη

In vitro διερεύνηση της αντιλειτουργικής θεραπευτικής δράσης του εκχυλίσματος *Medicago sativa*

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Η λεισμανίαση είναι μια ομάδα λοιμώξεων που προκαλούνται από διάφορα είδη παρασίτων του γένους *Leishmania*. Οι δερματικές εκδηλώσεις της νόσου μπορεί να προκαλέσουν πληγές μακράς διάρκειας, με δυσχερή αντιμετώπιση, συνεπώς είναι απαραίτητη η εύρεση νέων ουσιών που μπρούν να βοηθήσουν στην επούλωση. Ο στόχος αυτής της μελέτης είναι να διερευνήσει τη θεραπευτική δράση του εκχυλίσματος *Medicago sativa*. Τα παράσιτα *L. major* υποβλήθηκαν σε επεξεργασία με διαφορετικές συγκεντρώσεις φυτικού εκχυλίσματος *M. sativa* (5, 100, 250, 500 και 1000 μg / ml) για 24, 48 και 72 ώρες. Ο χαρακτηρισμός του εκχυλίσματος έγινε με υγρή χρωματογραφία αντίστροφης φάσης υψηλής απόδοσης (RP-HPLC). Οι τιμές IC₅₀ ήταν 566,62, 445,74 και 375,74 μετά από 24, 48 και 72 ώρες επώασης, αντίστοιχα. Τα αποτελέσματα έδειξαν ότι η επιβίωση του παρασίτου *L. major* μειώνεται αυξάνοντας τον χρόνο επώασης και / ή τη δοσολογία του φυτικού εκχυλίσματος. Η ανάλυση του εκχυλίσματος έδειξε ότι αυτό περιλαμβάνει φαινολικές και φλαβονοειδείς ενώσεις. Η συνολική τιμή των φαινολικών ενώσεων ήταν μεγαλύτερη από αυτή των φλαβονοειδών ενώσεων. Η αντι-*Leishmania* δραστηριότητα του εκχυλίσματος *M. sativa* πιθανά οφείλεται στην υψηλή συγκέντρωση φαινολικών ενώσεων και ειδικά καφεϊκού οξέος. Συμπερασματικά, σύμφωνα με τα αποτελέσματα της μελέτης, μπορεί να προταθεί ότι το εκχύλισμα *M. sativa* είναι ένα πιθανό φυτικό φάρμακο κατά των δερματικών βλαβών της λεισμανίασης.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

IC₅₀, *Leishmania*, *Medicago sativa*, φαινόλες, φλαβονοειδή, επούλωση δερματικών βλαβών

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